

ANTIMICROBIAL RESISTANCE IN POULTRY PRODUCTION: IMPACTS, CHALLENGES, AND ONE HEALTH APPROACH

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ABSTRACT

Antimicrobial resistance (AMR) is a growing global threat as microorganisms increasingly survive drugs designed to inhibit or destroy their activity. Livestock production contributes significantly due to heavy antimicrobial use, approximately 99502 tonnes in 2020 and is projected to reach nearly 107,472 tonnes of which 105,596 tons of antimicrobials will be consumed for animal production with overwhelming in Asia (67%), USA (80%), globally (70%) with 8% rise by 2030. India (2.2%) is the fifth-largest user of veterinary antimicrobials after China (45%), Brazil (7.9%), USA (7%) and Thailand (4.2%) with rapidly intensifying production in BRICS countries is expected to further drive usage. In animal health, the Americas, Asia (45%), and East Oceania use over 87% of veterinary antimicrobials, mainly tetracyclines and penicillins. In poultry farming, rising global demand for meat and eggs has led to extensive AMU (since mid-20th century) as AGPs. Misuse accelerates resistance through enzyme inactivation, target, and transport changes, allowing pathogens to enter the food chain and harm health. Improving biosecurity, hygiene, surveillance (One Health Approach) and adopting nutritional modulations to reduce reliance on antibiotics and curb AMR.

KEYWORDS: Poultry, Antimicrobial, Antibiotics, Biosecurity, Biotics

INTRODUCTION

Poultry sector evolving into a vibrant agribusiness industry and main supplier of high-quality protein diet “food-producing-farmed-animals” with 100 million (M) tonnes of meat and 1.3 trillion eggs annually having market value of \$378.84 billion in 20s23. Poultry is the second most widely consumed meat in the world (accounts 33%) will hold 41% by 2030, driven largely by Asia and Americas. In 2020 the global chicken population exceeded 33 billion, with 46% in Asia of which 851.8M population in India, with increased meat production of 5.18MT, egg production of 149.11B in 2024-25 having per capita availability of 7.5kg meat and 106 eggs, respectively (BAHS, 2025). As poultry production gains importance, dependence on antibiotics at subtherapeutic level as antibiotic growth promoters (AGPs) (since 1940s) as feed additives is also increased with annual consumption of antimicrobials about 148 mg/kg in the poultry diet.

The journey of antibiotic (coined by Selman Waksman) development began with Salvarsan (1910), penicillin-wonder drug (1928),

and sulphonamides (1930s), followed by the golden age (1950-60s) with streptomycin, tetracyclines, macrolides, and cephalosporins, over time newer drugs like Nafithromycin (2024) and Zaynich (2025) emerged. In 2020, WHO reported 50 antibiotics in trials, but only 6 (truly innovative) and 2 (multi drug-resistant bacteria). Antimicrobials revolutionized disease control *via* bacteriostatic and bactericidal, and improved poultry productivity *via* growth promoter action with increased usage in low-and middle-income countries. AMR enables microbes to survive drugs and spread widely, threatening health beyond veterinary concerns. Unregulated antibiotic use has accelerated AMR, creating a major global health emergency due to weak regulation and stewardship frameworks but modern medicine pushes towards “post-antibiotic era”. This article analyses poultry AMR, highlighting mechanisms, surveillance gaps, and nutrient-based mitigation strategies while safeguarding productivity (Hutchings *et al.*, 2019).

ANTIBIOTIC RESISTANCE AND MECHANISM OF ACTION

The antibiotics (against life) usage as growth promoters to boost their growth potential and productivity, reduce morbidity and mortality through their antibacterial activity by inhibition and disintegration of cell wall, inhibition of protein and DNA synthesis. Gram-positive bacteria lack lipopolysaccharide (LPS) outer membrane, so they have fewer barriers and simpler efflux systems compared to gram-negative bacteria where it have stronger protection through restricted drug entry, powerful efflux pumps, enzyme-based drug breakdown, and target modification. AMR (constitutive or induced) refers to reduced microbial sensitivity to antibiotics *via* increased minimum inhibitory concentration (MIC) or total insensitivity, caused by genetics *via* point mutations, phenotypic *via* reduced or complete antibiotic insensitivity, and sometimes *via* mutation changes over time. Bacteria employs target-site methylation *via* *erm* methylases, and *cf*r gene on 23S rRNA that reduce binding and resistance to multiple antibiotic classes. AMR develops naturally through genetic changes in pathogens but is accelerated by human misuse of antimicrobials to treat/ control infections. AMR threatens animal health by reducing treatment effectiveness and resistance arises by four major mechanisms includes inactivation, target alteration and chemical modification, efflux pumps (6 major families), and decreased permeability.

ENTRY POINTS AND KEY DRIVERS FOR AMR

Antimicrobials entry points with 5 major stages include feed and nutrition stage (medicated feed), disease prevention and health management (metaphylaxis, prophylaxis), therapeutic use in production phase (unsupervised usage), post-harvest and processing stage (residues, lack in withdrawal periods, absence of standard tests), environmental entry points (manure, litter, aquaculture effluent). Key drivers like unhygienic conditions, lack of veterinary treatment guidelines, inappropriate treatment, infrastructure gaps, limited antibiotic-sensitivity-test use, lack of training and awareness, unregulated supply chains, overuse and misuse, weak biosecurity, inadequate diagnostics, shortage of poultry-specific veterinary services, absence of record keeping data, limited regulations in feed mills, manufacturing, unqualified prescribers, inadequate disinfection protocols and

withdrawal periods, poor hygiene, weak regulation, and inadequate vaccination (Prescott, 2014).

BAN OF ANTIBIOTIC GROWTH PROMOTERS

Antibiotics (since 1946) at subtherapeutic level as growth promoters have improved poultry growth, feed efficiency (FE), and prevention of subclinical diseases prompting rapid integration of AGPs. In 1951, the U.S. FDA authorized routine antimicrobial inclusion in livestock feed without veterinary oversight, facilitating extensive, industry-wide adoption and unrestricted use. In 1970 Europe began regulating AGPs with standardizing under Directive 70/534, leads to ban in 2006 under Regulation 1831/2003 due to AMR concerns, allowing only coccidiostats and histomoniasis treatments. However, this results to inappropriate and excessive use of antibiotics as feed supplements, results in ban on AGPs in the EU (2006) under Regulation 1831/2003, USA-Veterinary Feed Directive (2017), China-AMU surveillance systems (2020), Thailand, South Korea, Vietnam (Tripartite Global Action Plan) and India is hotspot for AMR, understanding its causes and reducing inappropriate antibiotic use should be top priorities (Tolerance limits by FSSAI) with Food Safety and Standards Amendment Regulations 2018, allowing only coccidiostats and histomoniasis treatments underscore the urgent need for stronger surveillance and effective control.

GLOBAL AND NATIONAL ACTION PLAN ON AMR

Global initiatives like WHO- Global Antimicrobial Resistance Surveillance System (GLASS) with 5 strategic objectives (2015) *via* Enhancing Awareness and Scientific Understanding, Strengthening Evidence Through Surveillance and Research, Reducing Infection Burden Through Prevention and Hygiene, Promoting Rational and Responsible Antimicrobial Use, and Supporting Sustainable Investment and Innovation. World Organisation for Animal Health (WOAH) surveillance on AMR, European Surveillance of Veterinary Antimicrobial Consumption (ESVAC), U.S. National Antimicrobial Resistance Monitoring System (NARMS) and the Tripartite One Health collaborations provide frameworks, policy reforms and regulatory strengthening with international guidelines from Food and Agriculture Organization (FAO), and World Health Organization (WHO).

India's National Action Plan on AMR (NAP-AMR 2.0) in April 2017-2021 during "National Consultation to Operationalize Action Plan for AMR Containment" jointly by National Centre for Disease Control (NCDC), WHO, Ministry of Health and Family Welfare (MoHFW) with objectives of providing coordinated, and multisectoral strategy, and FSSAI (regulation of AM Residues in food), Indian Network for Fisheries and Animal Antimicrobial Resistance (INFAAR) network of 20 centers (11-livestock sector and 9-fisheries) monitors (surveillance on livestock and fisheries), ICMR and Antibiotic Stewardship Programs (ASPs) (promote rational antimicrobial use in healthcare), Central Pollution Control Board (CPCB) (regulate antibiotic residues in pharmaceutical effluents and effluent treatment plants), National Institute of Veterinary Epidemiology and Disease Informatics (NIVEDI), ban on colistin in animal feed, and Central Drugs Standard Control Organisation (CDSCO).

IMPLEMENTATION OF ANTIMICROBIAL STEWARDSHIP PROGRAMS

Implementing an effective ASPs in veterinary practice requires a coordinated, multidisciplinary approach by initiating fostering interdisciplinary collaboration, strict adherence to withdrawal periods, comprehensive record-keeping and control strategies (pre-and-post prescription) to ensure rational antimicrobial decision-making (AVMA). Stewardship develops evidence-based treatment guidelines, support clinicians with digital decision tools that integrate diagnostics to guide drug choice (first-line, restricted, reserve groups), therapy duration, timely feedback and revision of treatment protocols, implementation of antimicrobial rotation policies. The effectiveness of ASP with "5R" principles-right indication, right drug, right dose, right duration, and right frequency.

MITIGATION STRATEGIES FOR SUSTAINABLE POULTRY PRODUCTION

India must integrate farm-hospital-slaughterhouse data. Reducing AMU by strong biosecurity, all-in/all-out systems, innovations like genomic surveillance, precision farming, disease-resistant breeds, developing polices, monitor, license, surveillance, combat misinformation, controlling volume, foster cross-sectional learning, support research and innovation, and prudent antibiotic stewardship can reach the rising demand "antibiotic-free" or "organic food". AMR has driven development for alternative safe, effective,

and user-friendly therapies through improvement in "flock-health plan" reflects by adopting policy "prevention is better than cure" that can replace AGPs.

Mitigation strategies includes, *Biosecurity measures* by implementing hygiene protocols (regular cleaning, disinfection), and management of litter in "star rating system". *Precision antibiotic usage* by conducting antibiotic sensitivity tests, and using narrow-spectrum antibiotics. *Education and training* to farmers and farm workers on proper antibiotic use. *Surveillance systems* for monitoring antibiotic usage, tracking the prevalence and patterns of AMR, and identifying emerging resistant strains. G20 Summit of Agriculture Ministers Declarations (2023-24). *Codex guidelines* by Code of Practice to Minimize and Contain AMR, Guidelines on Integrated Monitoring and Surveillance of Foodborne AMR. *Veterinarians* in combating AMR through judicious antibiotic usage, stewardship, better diagnostics, and One Health collaboration. Already, Denmark, Netherlands and Sweden achieved >50% reduction in AMU through biosecurity, benchmarking, farmer education and AMR diagnostics. *Reaffirmed commitment* to eliminate non-therapeutic use in animals by 2030. *Indias commitments* in phase out growth promoters, consultations bridged sectors, integration of veterinary surveillance, adaptation of vaccines, industry led guidelines and farmer level AMR stewardship pilots. *Certifications* like "antibiotic-free," "raised without antibiotics," and "residue-safe" production, Certified Responsible Antibiotic Use (CRAU) in USA, "Shrimp Without Antibiotics" (MPEDAs). *Rapid innovations* in diagnostics, digital traceability, phage therapy, immunostimulants, vaccines, and feed additives (measures (Rahal and Kumar 2021).

NOVEL THERAPEUTIC INTERVENTIONS TO COUNTERACT AMR

Various novel therapeutics that reduce dependence on antibiotics, includes *Efflux Pump Inhibition* (EPI) offers a promising way to combat antibiotic resistance by reducing drug expulsion, restoring antibiotic efficacy, and enhancing bacterial sensitivity through synthetic or natural modulators (plant alkaloid). *Microbial Quorum sensing* (QS) regulates bacterial communication, virulence, and resistance. Targeting QS systems (PhoP/PhoQ). *Vaccines* (lowers antibiotic dependence and decrease zoonotic transmission) to control AMR by preventing infections, reducing antibiotic use, and limiting resistant strain

emergence. Moreover, live vaccines can introduce new species or unexpected pathogens into flock. *Phage and nanoparticle* therapies in livestock are attracting biotech investments. *Immunomodulation* enhances disease resistance and reduces AMR indirectly by activating macrophages and reprogramming innate immune responses (Kurva, 2025).

NUTRITIONAL MODULATION: ALTERNATIVES TO ANTIBIOTICS

Nutrient Modulations for healthy gut, immunity, and balanced microbiome with restrictions on in-feed antibiotics by strategically adjusting dietary nutrients-energy, protein, vitamins, minerals, and fiber by using additives like various biotics, EOs, and AMPs that suppress/competitive exclusion of pathogens (antimicrobial), anti-inflammatory (reduce gut irritation and damage), reinforce gut integrity, increase synthesis of volatile fatty acids, and enhance B-vitamin synthesis *via* gut-brain axis can reflect the reduced dependence on antibiotics which encourage future to “antibiotic free era”.

1. Probiotics/ Direct Fed Microbials (DFM)

Probiotics (for life) are “live microorganisms like *Bifidobacterium spp.*, *Lactococcus spp.*, *Lactobacillus spp.* (discovered by Dr. Pierre Boucard’s), *Bacillus spp.* (endospores), *Streptococcus spp.*, *Candida spp.* that provide the host a health benefit when administered in appropriate amounts” with positive impact on production, regulation of intestinal microflora and pathogen inhibition, immunomodulation, and antimicrobial (bacitracin destroy peptidoglycan layer, bacilysin inhibits *E. coli*) by competitive inhibition applied as drops, sprays, granules, tablets, capsules, or powder sachets having market value of USD 46.55billion but acts like “double-edged sword”.

2. Paraprobiotics/ Ghost probiotics

Paraprobiotics are the non-viable/inactivated microbial cells or cell fractions, non-culturable and immunologically active cell to confer health benefits to host by modulation of humoral immunity, increase goblet cells, antimicrobial, phagocyte activation (lysozyme), and antistress.

3. Prebiotics

Prebiotics are “non-digestible food component that boosts health by helping specific beneficial gut bacteria grow or stay active/fermented in colon that produce lactic acid, SCFA by β -glucans, xylose oligosaccharides (XOS) can

indirect modulate the HPA-axis that have immunomodulation, antimicrobial and lowers the concentration of cortisol and cholesterol, improves FE. Refined Functional Carbohydrates (RFC), composed of MOS, D-mannose, and β -glucan from the cell wall of *Saccharomyces cerevisiae* (20-30% of dry cell mass).

4. Stimbiotics

Stimbiotics (xylanase + XOS) are an emerging class of feed additives, designed to selectively stimulate gut fiber-degrading bacteria. Unlike traditional prebiotics, stimbiotics are used at much lower doses (20gm/tonne) which acts by oligosaccharide signalling, microbiome adaptation, and enzymatic action. These improve FCR (3-5 points), enhance nutrient digestibility, gut integrity, reduce inflammation, and promote beneficial bacteria while limiting pathogens.

5. Synbiotics

In 1995, Gibson and Roberfroid introduced “synbiotic” are combination of probiotics and prebiotics benefits the host by improving survival, gut balance, protection, supplementation of nutrient-energy, reduce interleukins and IFN γ and lesion scores during infection.

6. Phytobiotics/ PhytoGenics

Phytobiotics are “natural compounds from herbs, spices and plants which are natural alternatives to synthetic AGPs” used as prophylactic. Essential Oils (EOs) “are aromatic, volatile liquids extracted from plants by steam distillation” acts as anti-inflammatory, anti-parasitic. Lycopene (carotenoid in tomatoes), Resveratrol (polyphenols in grapes, peanut, turmeric, berries), Curcumin (polyphenols in turmeric), Epigallocatechin gallate (polyphenols in green tea extract) with antioxidant, anti-inflammatory, antistress action improves growth, FE, and immunogenic.

7. Postbiotics/ next generation Probiotics/ *ngPro's*

Postbiotics are “the nutritional non-viable soluble metabolites secreted as byproducts from probiotics that confer a health benefit to the host” from the concept of 3R’s (Replacement, Reduction, Refinement) includes family Lactobacillaceae (33 genera) offering anti-inflammatory, antimicrobial, immunomodulation, anti-proliferative, antioxidant, anti-stress, and growth promoter. Advanced with postbiotics nanoparticles (*ngPro's*-NPs) to deliver bioactive components with therapeutic action.

Fig 1: One Health Approach to combat AMR

Fig 2: Mechanism of action of Biotics

8. Superfood/ All in One Feed and Osmolytes

Superfood from spirulina (*Arthrospira platensis*) blue green algae improves production, shank pigment, reduced lipid content and transaminases, and higher protein concentration. Osmolytes like Betaine (zwitterionic 4° NH₃ in living organisms), Taurine (2-aminoethanesulfonic acid in animal tissue), L-Glutamine (conditionally essential

amino acid synthesized by liver, muscles) acts as “nitrogen shuttle”,

Astaxanthin (AST) (blood-red carotenoid from *Phaffia rhodozyma* yeast). These enhance antioxidant defense, osmoregulation, anti-inflammatory, membrane stability, Calcium homeostasis, and overall stress resilience.

9. Bacteriophages

Bacteriophages are viruses that infect and replicate inside bacteria which are extremely abundant in nature (10³¹ phage particles in the biosphere) about 10 times more than the total number of bacterial cells. Based on their interaction with bacteria, as lytic (virulent) or lysogenic (temperate) or both in lambda phage of *E. coli*. In the lytic cycle (preferred for therapy), phages infect, replicate, and lyse bacteria but in lysogenic cycle, phage DNA integrates and replicates without killing the cell.

10. Antimicrobial peptides

Antimicrobial peptides (AMPs) are naturally occurring or synthetic molecules that provide a promising alternative to traditional antibiotics in poultry production. These peptides are part of the innate immune system in animals and demonstrate broad-spectrum antimicrobial and antiparasitic activity, immunogenic, improve growth, FE and gut integrity.

CONCLUSION

AMR represents one of the gravest challenges in poultry sector that intensifies the emergence of resistant bacteria to tackle AMR needs policy enforcement, coordinated efforts, adopting a One Health approach (human-animal-environment), awareness, non-antibiotic feed solutions to reduce antibiotic use and improving food safety. Innovations strengthen trust and food security to curb AMR.

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